

SUPERSATURATION LIMITS OF SOLUTIONS. PART III.

BY RAMA GOPAL AND A. C. CHATTERJEE

It has been shown that the equation of Jones and Partington and hence the equation $\lambda_0(T_s - T) = 2M\sigma T_s / \rho r$ derived therefrom is applicable to supersaturated solutions of electrolytes and that the values of the heats of solution at ordinary temperatures, instead of those at the absolute zero, may be employed for approximate calculations.

Jones and Partington (*Phil. Mag.*, 1915, 29, 35) have shown that equation (1) rests on the consideration of

$$\begin{aligned} T &= C \left(1 - \frac{2M\sigma}{\rho\lambda_0 r} \right) \\ &= T_s \left(1 - \frac{2M\sigma}{\rho\lambda_0 r} \right) \end{aligned} \quad \dots (1)$$

the Ostwald-Freundlich equation (1, a) (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1909, 34, 497; Freundlich, "Kapillarchemie," 1909, p. 114), which is applicable to dilute solutions of non-electrolytes.

$$\frac{RT}{M} \ln \frac{S_2}{S_1} = \frac{2\sigma}{\rho} \left(\frac{1}{r_2} - \frac{1}{r_1} \right) \quad \dots (1, a)$$

(The terms in the above equations have their usual significance). Hence the use of the equation,

$$\lambda_0(T_s - T) = \frac{2M\sigma}{\rho r} T_s \quad \dots (2)$$

which is based on equation (1) (*cf. J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 183), in the aqueous solutions of electrolytes appears at the first sight to be quite unjustified. Besides, λ_0 in (1) is the heat of solution at the absolute zero and therefore the substitution of the values of the heats of solution at ordinary temperatures for λ_0 in (2) may be a matter of serious objections. These two points were not fully discussed before due to the fact that the authors of the theory itself applied equation (1) to solutions of Glauber's salt (*loc. cit.*). However, the applicability of equations (1) and (2) to solutions of electrolytes and the use of the ordinary heats of solution λ_0 appear to be justified from the following considerations.

Ostwald-Freundlich equation can be reduced to the form

$$\frac{RT}{M} \ln \frac{S}{S_\infty} = \frac{2\sigma}{\rho r} \quad \dots (3)$$

where S denotes the solubility, of particles of radius r and S_∞ , the solubility of those of radius ∞ , i.e., the ordinary solubility. Jones (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1913, 82, 448) has shown that for electrolytes the general Ostwald-Freundlich equation becomes:

$$\frac{2\sigma}{\rho} \left(\frac{1}{r_2} - \frac{1}{r_1} \right) = \frac{RT}{M} \left[\ln(n-1)(\alpha_1 - \alpha_2) - \frac{n}{m-1} \ln \frac{1-\alpha_1}{1-\alpha_2} + \frac{m}{m-1} \ln \frac{\alpha_1}{\alpha_2} \right]$$

where α_1 and α_2 are the degrees of dissociation at concentrations S_1 and S_2 , n , the number of ions per molecule of the electrolyte in question and m , the constant of the Storch's equation namely,

$$\frac{1-\alpha}{v} = k \left(\frac{\alpha}{v} \right)^m$$

However, assuming the degree of dissociation α to be constant within a small range of concentrations, a simpler equation of Mack and Dundon (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **45**, 2479) namely,

$$(1 - \alpha + n\alpha) \ln \frac{S_2}{S_1} = \frac{2M\sigma}{\rho RT} \left(\frac{1}{r_2} - \frac{1}{r_1} \right)$$

can be employed without undue loss of accuracy instead of the rigorous equation of Jones. Hence equation (3) becomes

$$(1 - \alpha + n\alpha) \ln \frac{S}{S_\infty} = \frac{2M\sigma}{\rho r RT} \quad \dots (4)$$

Equation (4) can be written as

$$i \ln S = \frac{2M\sigma}{\rho r RT} + i \ln S_\infty$$

or

$$\ln S = \frac{2M\sigma}{i\rho r RT} + \ln S_\infty \quad \dots (5)$$

where i denotes $(1 - \alpha + n\alpha)$. For $\ln S_\infty$ one must now substitute the expression $-\frac{\lambda_0}{iRT} + \frac{a'}{iR} \ln T + C'$ instead of the expression $-\frac{\lambda_0}{RT} + \frac{a}{R} \ln T + C$ as the latter expression holds only for undissociated substances (Hardman and Partington, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, **99**, 1771). In these expressions a , a' , C and C' are constants. Considering the heat of solution to be constant within a small range of concentrations and temperatures the above expression can be further reduced to $-\frac{\lambda}{iRT} + C'$ by directly integrating the equation $\frac{d \ln S}{dT} = \frac{\lambda}{RT^2}$ where λ denotes the heat of solution at temperatures in the neighbourhood of T . Hence at temperature T equation (5) simplifies to

$$\ln S_T = \frac{2M\sigma}{i\rho R r T} - \frac{\lambda}{iRT} + C'$$

or

$$S_T = A \exp. \left[\frac{2M\sigma}{i\rho R r T} - \frac{\lambda}{iRT} + C' \right] \quad \dots (6)$$

* Activities may be used instead of concentrations (*cf.* Partington, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, **36**, 1853; Kolthoff, *ibid.*, 457). In this case, assuming strong electrolytes to be completely dissociated at all concentrations, the equation of Mack and Dundon becomes

$$n \ln \frac{S_2 \gamma_2}{S_1 \gamma_1} = \frac{2M\sigma}{\rho RT} \left(\frac{1}{r_2} - \frac{1}{r_1} \right)$$

where γ_1 and γ_2 are the mean activity coefficients at the two concentrations. Now equation (4) given above will take the form

$$n \ln \frac{S \gamma}{S_\infty \gamma_\infty} = \frac{2M\sigma}{\rho RT} \quad \dots (4')$$

Now assuming γ and γ_∞ to be nearly the same, as activities do not change very rapidly with concentration, (4') simplifies to

$$n \ln \frac{S}{S_\infty} = \frac{2M\sigma}{\rho RT}$$

The rest is simple.

Similarly at $T + \delta T$, $S_{T + \delta T} = i \exp. \left[\frac{2M(\sigma + \delta\sigma)}{iR(\rho + \delta\rho)(r + \delta r)(T + \delta T)} - \frac{\lambda}{iR(T + \delta T)} + C' \right]$... (7)

But $S_r = S_{(T + \delta T)}$

Consequently $\frac{2M\sigma}{iR\rho T} - \frac{\lambda}{iRT} + C' = \frac{2M(\sigma + \delta\sigma)}{iR(\rho + \delta\rho)(r + \delta r)(T + \delta T)} - \frac{\lambda}{iR(T + \delta T)} + C'$

or $\frac{2M\sigma}{\rho r T} - \frac{\lambda}{T} = \frac{2M(\sigma + \delta\sigma)}{(\rho + \delta\rho)(r + \delta r)(T + \delta T)} - \frac{\lambda}{(T + \delta T)}$... (8)

Thus the factor i completely vanishes and also λ now denotes the heat of solution at ordinary temperatures. Further simplification of (8) and neglecting of the terms involving infinitesimals of higher orders leads to the equation

$$\left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{\rho r \lambda}{2M\sigma T} \right) \delta T = \frac{\partial\sigma}{\sigma} - \frac{\partial\rho}{\rho} - \frac{\partial r}{r}$$
 ... (9)

But $\frac{\partial\sigma}{\sigma} - \frac{\partial\rho}{\rho} = 0$ (approx.)

Therefore $\left(\frac{\rho r \lambda}{2M\sigma T} - \frac{1}{T} \right) \delta T = -\frac{\partial r}{r}$... (10)

which on integration gives $T = C \left(1 - \frac{1}{kr} \right)$... (11)

where $k = \frac{\rho r \lambda}{2M\sigma}$ and C is a constant.

If T equals the saturation temperature T_s , $r = \infty$. Hence $C = T_s$. Therefore (11) can be written as

$$T = T_s \left(1 - \frac{1}{kr} \right)$$

which is exactly the relationship obtained by Jones and Partington, λ now being the heat of solution at ordinary temperatures. From the last equation it is easy to obtain

$$\lambda(T_s - T) = \frac{2M\sigma}{\rho r} T_s$$
 ... (12)

PRESIDENT :

B. B. DEY, D.Sc., F.I.C.

VICE-PRESIDENTS :

(who have filled the office of President)

SIR S. S. BHATNAGAR, KT., O.B.E., F.R.S., D.Sc., F. INST. P., F.I.C.	GILBERT J. FOWLER, D.Sc., F.I.C.
SIR U. N. BRAHMACHARI, KT., M.A., M.D., PH.D.	SIR J. C. GHOSH, KT., D.Sc., F.N.I.
N. R. DHAR, D.Sc., DR.ES.SC., F.I.C.	SIR P. C. RAY, KT., C.I.E., D.Sc., PH.D.
	H. K. SEN, D.Sc., D.I.C.
	B. K. SINGH, Sc.D., F.I.C.

VICE-PRESIDENTS :

P. C. MITTER, M.A., PH.D.	J. N. RAY, D.Sc., PH.D., F.I.C.
K. G. NAIK, D.Sc., F.I.C.	R. C. RAY, D.Sc., F.I.C.

HONY. SECRETARY :

B. N. GHOSH, D.Sc.

HONY. TREASURER :

SUDHAMOY GHOSH, D.Sc., F.I.C.

MEMBERS OF THE COUNCIL :

B. AHMAD, M.Sc., Ph.D.	K. L. MOUDGILL, D.Sc., F.I.C.
S. N. CHAKRAVARTI, D.Phil., D.Sc., F.I.C.	P. NEOGI, M.A., Ph.D.
J. K. CHOWDHURY, M.Sc., Ph.D.	MATA PRASAD, D.Sc., F.I.C.
MRS. SHEILA DHAR, M.Sc.	B. SANJIVA RAO, M.A., Ph.D.
M. GOSWAMI, M.A., DR.ES.SC.	S. P. SEN, M.Sc.
B. C. GUHA, D.Sc., Ph.D.	T. R. SESHADRI, M.A., Ph.D.
P. C. GUHA, D.Sc.	V. SUBRAHMANYAN, D.Sc., F.I.C.
S. S. JOSHI, D.Sc.	K. VENKATARAMAN, D.Sc., Ph.D., F.I.C.
A. N. KAPPANNA, D.Sc.	N. A. YAJNIK, M.A., D.Sc., A.I.C.

HONY. EDITORS :

P. K. BOSE, D.Sc.
P. B. SARKAR, DR.ES. SC.

BOARD OF ASSOCIATE EDITORS :

K. P. BASU, D.Sc., Ph.D.	P. RAY, M.A., F.N.I.
SIR S. S. BHATNAGAR, KT., O.B.E., F.R.S., D.Sc., F. INST P., F.I.C.	P. C. MITTER, M.A., Ph.D.
B. B. DEY, D.Sc., F.I.C.	MATA PRASAD, D.Sc., F.I.C.
N. R. DHAR, D.Sc., DR.ES.SC., F.I.C.	H. K. SEN, D.Sc., D.I.C.
SIR J. C. GHOSH, KT., D.Sc. F.N.I.	N. C. SEN-GUPTA, D.Sc.
P. C. GUHA, D.Sc.	S. SIDDIQUI, Ph.D.
A. N. KAPPANNA, D.Sc.	K. VENKATARAMAN, D.Sc., Ph.D., F.I.C.

HONY. AUDITORS :

T. K. RAICHAUDHURY, B.Sc., LL.B., A.C.A.
P. C. NANDI, M.A., B.Sc., A.C.A., R.A
(Chartered Accountants)

ASST. EDITORS :

D. CHAKRAVARTI, D.Sc.
S. N. MUKHERJEE, M.Sc.

ASST. SECRETARY :

G. BANERJEE, M.Sc.